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Abstract

This study investigated whether Facebook addiction can predict anxiety and depression among young adults in Dhaka city. A questionnaire package consisting of the Bangla versions of the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale, Beck Anxiety Inventory, and Beck Depression Inventory was administered to 200 undergraduate and postgraduate students (50% male, 50% female; mean age = 21.73 years) selected via purposive sampling. Reliability analysis demonstrated high internal consistency across all three instruments. An independent sample t-test revealed significant gender differences in Facebook addiction, with male students scoring higher than females, though no significant gender differences were found for anxiety and depression. Correlation analysis showed a significant positive association of Facebook addiction with both anxiety ($r = 0.63$) and depression ($r = 0.41$). Furthermore, linear regression analysis revealed that Facebook addiction significantly predicts 17.1% of the variance in anxiety and 20.8% of the variance in depression.

Facebook Addiction Predicting Anxiety and Depression among Young Adults

Farjana Begum¹, Muhammad Kamal Uddin², Shakila Parvin Bristy³ & Momtaz Sultana⁴

Abstract

The present study tested whether facebook addiction can predict anxiety and depression among young adults. A questionnaire package comprised of Bangla versions of Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale, Beck Anxiety Inventory and Beck Depression Inventory, along with a Personal Information Form were administered to 200 undergraduate and post graduate students of Dhaka city. Among them 50% were boys and 50% were female with a mean age of 21.73 years (SD = 1.73). The reliability analysis revealed high internal consistency of all 3 measuring instruments (Cronbach alpha was 0.94, 0.86, and 0.85 respectively for facebook addiction, anxiety and depression). Independent sample *t* test revealed significant gender differences in facebook addiction. So, subsequent analyses were carried out on entire sample. Correlation analysis showed significant association of anxiety and depression with Facebook addiction ($r = 0.63$ and 0.41 , respectively); the higher the facebook addiction, the higher is the anxiety and depression. Linear regression analysis revealed that facebook addiction can predict 17.1% variance in anxiety and 20.8% variance in depression among young adults in Dhaka city. Facebook addiction made a significant contribution to the variance in both anxiety and depression. The findings have implications for parents and guardians, teachers, mental health professionals, educators, and policy makers.

Keywords: facebook addiction, anxiety and depression

Social networking sites especially facebook has become an essential part of the lives of many people now-a-days. The rising fame of Facebook has turn into an attractive topic for social research, which can be seen in the growing number of publications on that issue. Through Facebook people can communicate with others who have related interests and it helps them for sharing their thoughts and keeps updated about their contacts' life (Raacke & Bonds-Raacke, 2008). In this social networking site, people can connect with others through updating status, poking, they can share something on their timeline as well as they can send messages with each other (Papacharissi & Mendelsohn, 2011). In according to a finding of 2015 published on Facebook (<http://www.statista.com>), there are 1.49 billion people worldwide who use Facebook actively. Although Facebook is helpful in promoting communication, maintaining friendship and keep up-to-date with new information, in the contrary, it has many negative impacts on an individual's life.

Facebook addiction can be defined as facing complexity to limit and to control the amount of time spending in Facebook (Lee, Cheung & Thadani, 2012). According to Andreassen et al. (2012), the impact of facebook addiction can be temper change, salience, patience increase, withdrawal, conflict and deterioration. Some signs of Facebook addiction are: over-sharing, checking one's facebook whenever possible, overly concerned with Facebook image, reporting on facebook, spending hours browsing through facebook every day, mad rush to add more friends, compromising offline social life

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and many more. People face many social and psychological problems as a result of Facebook addiction (Kuss and Griffiths, 2011). Facebook affected individuals' emotional situations negatively (Sagioglou and Greitemeyer, 2014). Kross et al. (2013) found that excessive use of facebook deteriorate persons' way of thinking of living the moment and also hamper their feelings of life contentment. Furthermore, people who are addicted to facebook have lower satisfaction toward their life (Bevan, Gomez and Sparks, 2014).

Excessive use of Facebook may lead to depressive symptoms as well as anxiety based problem. In a study on Pakistani students it was found that there was a linear interaction among facebook addiction and anxiety as well as depression (Zaffar, Mahmood, Saleem & Zakaria, 2015). Anxiety is an unpleasant emotional state characterized by feelings of tension, physical changes and worried thoughts like increased blood pressure. Depression, trouble in sleeping, substance abuse, digestive problems, headaches, social isolation, poor quality of life, and even suicidal tendency may result as untreated anxiety (Strickland, 2001). Moreover, some other studies also found that the facebook addiction is intertwined with depression (Hong et al., 2014). Several symptoms of depression includes; feeling sad, empty or hopeless, lack of interests, lack of sleep or excessive sleep, exhaustion or tiredness, feelings of unimportance, a psychomotor anxiety or retardation, excessive guilt, inability to think properly, lack of concentrate or indecision, frequent thought of loss, frequent suicidal thought etc. As a result of facebook addiction, depression often makes us anxious and anxiety often makes us depressed.

Facebook is an interesting topic additionally a concerning issue nowadays especially among young adults in Bangladesh. The impact associated with facebook addiction can be high in physical, psychological and social terms especially the problem becomes more severe in Bangladesh where parental check and balance is not very strict. Researchers have predicted an association of facebook addiction with anxiety and depression. More facebook addicted people may be more depressed and anxious and vice versa. Facebook addiction leads to anxiety as well as depression among young adults which in turn causes low self-esteem, lack of motivation, irritability, suicidal tendency, trouble of sleeping, and social isolation. Moreover facebook addiction is seen to be more intense in the urban areas like Dhaka city because of its excessive use than in rural area. Due to depression and anxiety caused by facebook addiction, young generation may engaged in several immoral acts and crimes which is a matter of big concern now-a-days in Bangladesh. Current study expects to find out the relationship among facebook addiction, anxiety, and depression in young adults of Dhaka city. Besides, this research will give a message to the society about the consequences of facebook addiction with anxiety and depression and will be served as valuable source to reduce this as well as to create awareness.

The purposes of the present study were:

1. To investigate whether there is any gender difference in facebook addiction, anxiety and depression.
2. To investigate whether there is any relationship among facebook addiction, anxiety and depression.
3. To investigate whether anxiety and depression would be predicted by Facebook addiction.

Method

Participants

The participants of this study comprised a total number of 200 undergraduate and post graduate students from both public and private university of Dhaka city. Purposive sampling technique was used

to select the respondents. Their age range was from 18-26 years (with a mean of 21.73 and SD of 1.73). Their level of education was undergraduate to Masters. About 4.5% of the respondents identified themselves as from a lower class, 25.5% as lower middle class, 61.5% as middle class and 8% as higher middle class family background.

Measuring Instruments

All participants in the research responded to a questionnaire package comprising of three self-report questionnaires along with a personal information form. The three measures include: (1) the Bangla version of Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS), (2) the Bangla version Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) and (3) the Bangla version Beck Depression Inventory (BDI). All of the questionnaires were translated into Bangla language as the first language of all the participants was Bangla. A brief description of each measure is given below.

Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (BFAS)

The Bangla version (Begum, Uddin & Bristy, 2017) of Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale (Andreassen, Torsheim, Brunborg, & Pallesen, 2012) contains 18 items to assess six core symptoms of addiction as salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse. Three items were formed for each of these criteria. Addiction is present when a person meets these precise criteria during twelve months period. Participants rated each item using 5-point continuum scale: 1 (very rarely), 2 (rarely), 3 (sometimes), 4 (often) and 5 (very often). Higher score means more addiction and lower score means less addiction. The possible score ranges is 18 to 90. The standard cutoffs were, 0-19: natural, 20-39: mild, 40-69: moderate and 70-90: severe level of facebook addiction. The reliability of translated version of BFAS was highly consistent. The Bangla version of the scale shows reliability with high internal consistency Cronbach's alpha 0.94. The Bangla version of the scale Cronbach's alpha was also found for six subscales (salience .71, tolerance .81, mood modification .81, relapse .75, withdrawal .78 and conflict .78) of the BFAS separately.

Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI)

The Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI) (Beck, Steer & Garbin, 1988) used in the study measures clinical anxiety. It is a self-reporting 21-item scale which includes symptoms that are common in anxiety. The respondents are asked to indicate how much they had been bothered by the items in the last four weeks. It has four response options ranging from 0 (*Not at all*) to 3 (*Severely, I could barely stand it*). So, the possible score ranges is 0 to 63; higher the score means higher the anxiety. The standardized cutoffs were: 0-9: minimal anxiety, 10-16: mild anxiety, 17-29: moderate anxiety, 30-63: severe anxiety. The scale was translated into Bangla language by Uddin, & Shama (2017). The Bangla translation of the scale shows reliability with high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .86$).

Beck Depression Inventory (BDI)

The Bangla version (Uddin & Ahmed, 2013) of the Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) (Beck, Steer, Garbin, 1988) was used to assess the depression of participants. It is a self-administered scale with 21 items. The items include but not limited to mood, pessimism, libido, sleep disturbances and many more. These 4-point scale ranges from 0 to 3, with the possible minimum and maximum scores are 0-63, respectively where the higher score indicates higher level of depression. The standardized cutoffs used differed from the original: - 0-13: minimal depression, 14-19: mild depression, 20-28: moderate depression, 29-63: severe depression. The Bangla translation of the scale used for the present study also shows high internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .85$).

Procedure

For collection of data permission was asked from the appropriate authorities of the university via written letter. Before giving the questionnaire package to any participant, they were briefed verbally about the purpose of the study. After informing the purpose of the study they were requested to read the instruction carefully and express their responses by giving tick marks on consequent boxes. They were also requested not to omit any item in the scales and to answer all the items by telling that there is no right or wrong answer to any item. It was confirmed that confidentiality would be strictly maintained and these would be used only on research purpose. Each of the questionnaires took about 10 minutes to fill up. Participants were thanked after the collection of data.

Results

The main purposes of the study was to see whether there is any difference in facebook addiction, anxiety and depression according to gender; whether there is any relationship of facebook addiction with anxiety and depression; and whether facebook addiction can predicts anxiety and depression. Correlation, *t* test and regression were used to do the analysis.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics and gender differences in major variables

Variables	<i>n</i>	Male		<i>n</i>	Female		df	<i>t</i>
		Mean	SD		Mean	SD		
Facebook Addiction	99	20.87	11.06	101	19.04	10.69	198	2.94*
Anxiety	99	39.39	14.16	101	40.93	16.02	198	.72
Depression	99	18.53	10.29	101	17.35	11.63	198	-.76

* $P < 0.05$

Table 1 shows that, facebook addiction of male student ($M = 20.87$) is noticed higher than that of female student ($M = 19.04$). Again the mean score of anxiety and depressive behavior of female student ($M = 40.93, 17.35$) is higher than that of male student ($M = 39.39, 18.53$). The results suggest that there is a significant difference between male and female in facebook addiction.

Table 2

Correlation among Facebook Addiction, Anxiety and Depression

Variable	1	2	3
1. Facebook addiction	1		
2. Anxiety	.63**	1	
3. Depression	.41**	.46**	1

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results shown in Table 2 represents that, facebook addiction, anxiety and depression are significantly correlated with one another. Facebook addiction is positively correlated with anxiety and depression and the index of correlation was $r = .63, .41$ are significant at .01 level.

Table 3

Linear regression analysis of facebook addiction on anxiety

Model	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>B</i>	<i>SEB</i>	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p value</i>
Anxiety	.414	.171	.298	.047	.4146	.393	.000

$F = 40.876, p < 0.000$

Table 3 indicated that the unstandardized regression coefficient ($B = .298$) of anxiety associated with facebook addiction indicating that facebook addiction increased .298 unit, with each one unit increased in anxiety. On the other hand, the standard regression coefficient ($\beta = .414$) of anxiety for youth associated with facebook addiction indicated that facebook addiction increased .414 unit with each one standard unit increased in anxiety. Again 17.1% of the variation in anxiety could be explained by the variation of facebook addiction. R^2 revealed that only facebook addiction explained 17.1% of the variation in anxiety.

Table 4*Linear regression analysis of facebook addiction on depression*

Model	R	R^2	B	SEB	β	t	p value
Depression	.456	.208	.331	.046	.4567	.207	.000

$F = 51.942, p < 0.000$

Table 4 indicated that the unstandardized regression coefficient ($B = .331$) of depression associated with facebook addiction indicated that facebook addiction increased .331 unit, with each one unit increased in depressive behavior. On the other hand, the standard regression coefficient ($\beta = .456$) of depressive behavior associated with facebook addiction indicated that facebook addiction increased .456 unit with each one standard unit increased in depressive behavior. Again 20.8% of the variation in depressive behavior could be explained by the variation of facebook addiction. R^2 revealed that only facebook addiction explained 20.8% of the variation in depression.

Discussion

The present study was designed to explore three research purposes. There were two different significant findings about this research purpose. Firstly, t -test table showed that, there was significant gender difference between male and female in using Facebook. Males (20.87) are more addicted to Facebook than females (19.04). Most of the research findings about facebook addiction show females are more prone to facebook or other social networking sites than males. In this research we have found contrary which may be due to our culture in which males are more outgoing and social than females, they want to make more friends than females. In Bangladesh many females are from conservative families where they face many restrictions in making friends, using social networking sites. The result is consistent with the findings of Mazman et al. (2011), who found that males are more addicted to facebook for making new friends or contacts than females (Mazman and Usluel, 2011).

Secondly, t -test revealed that there is no significant gender deference in anxiety and depression. At present, gender is not considered as an important cause of anxiety and depression. So, both male and female face same level of anxiety and depression either higher or lower. There are some differences between the study findings of our culture and foreign culture. Anxiety and depression are found associated with one another in many cases because there is always found a comorbidity between anxiety and depression. This finding is consistent with some other findings where it was found that in case of minor anxiety and depression there is no difference in males and females (Angst; Gamma; Gastpar; Lépine; Mendlewicz; and Tylee, 2002).

The second purpose of this study was to investigate whether there is any relationship among facebook addiction, anxiety and depression. Results show that facebook addiction is positively

correlated with anxiety and depression among young adults. This finding is consistent with Zaffar, Mahmood, Saleem and Zakaria (2015), in which they found that those who were spending maximum time on Facebook were suffering more from depression and anxiety.

The third purpose of the study was to investigate whether anxiety and depression would be predicted by Facebook addiction. Results show that, facebook addiction explained 17.1% and 20.8% of the variation in anxiety and depression respectively. This finding is also supported by previous studies. Personality, gender, procrastination, boredom and values may affect the amount of time people spend on Facebook. There is a linear interaction between Facebook addiction and anxiety as well as depression (Zaffar, Mahmood, Saleem & Zakaria, 2015).

In Bangladeshi context, people especially young generations spend more and more time on Facebook in their leisure period. Young adults are the pillar of a nation. They need support to be mentally healthy, happy and light-hearted to lead a meaningful life. This study can help us to identify people who are suffering from different level of anxiety and depression. As a result, necessary treatment can be provided in the treatment of such disorders. Moreover, the positive relationship among anxiety, depression and facebook addiction can help affected people to be aware of the misuses of Facebook. The findings have implications for parents and guardians, teachers, mental health professionals, educators, and policy makers.

Now-a-days an increasing number of young adults seek help from different helping professionals like psychologists, sociologists and psychiatrists due to facing depression and anxiety and as a result of which Facebook addiction is increasing day by day. However, the current study exposed heuristic values for future researches and theory development by illustrating the relationship among facebook addiction, anxiety and depression among young adults.

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